

Atlas Lisažuovih figura

— degenerisane krive —

Predrag Pejović

24.09.2015, 17:50

Slika 1: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(\omega t)$

Slika 2: $x = -4 \operatorname{div} \cos(\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(\omega t)$

Slika 3: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(2\omega t)$

Slika 4: $x = -4 \operatorname{div} \cos(\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(2\omega t)$

Slika 5: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(3\omega t)$

Slika 6: $x = -4 \operatorname{div} \cos(\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(3\omega t)$

Slika 7: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(4\omega t)$

Slika 8: $x = -4 \operatorname{div} \cos(\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(4\omega t)$

Slika 9: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(5\omega t)$

Slika 10: $x = -4 \operatorname{div} \cos(\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(5\omega t)$

Slika 11: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(6\omega t)$

Slika 12: $x = -4 \operatorname{div} \cos(\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(6\omega t)$

Slika 13: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(7\omega t)$

Slika 14: $x = -4 \operatorname{div} \cos(\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(7\omega t)$

Slika 15: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(8\omega t)$

Slika 16: $x = -4 \operatorname{div} \cos(\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(8\omega t)$

Slika 17: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(9 \omega t)$

Slika 18: $x = -4 \operatorname{div} \cos(\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(9 \omega t)$

Slika 19: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(10 \omega t)$

Slika 20: $x = -4 \operatorname{div} \cos(\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(10 \omega t)$

Slika 21: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(2\omega t), y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(\omega t)$

Slika 22: $x = -4 \operatorname{div} \cos(2\omega t), y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(\omega t)$

Slika 23: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(2\omega t), y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(2\omega t)$

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Slika 29: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(2\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(5\omega t)$

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Slika 32: $x = -4 \operatorname{div} \cos(2\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(6\omega t)$

Slika 33: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(2\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(7\omega t)$

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Slika 37: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(2\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(9\omega t)$

Slika 38: $x = -4 \operatorname{div} \cos(2\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(9\omega t)$

Slika 39: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(2\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(10\omega t)$

Slika 40: $x = -4 \operatorname{div} \cos(2\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(10\omega t)$

Slika 41: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(3\omega t), y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(\omega t)$

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Slika 43: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(3\omega t), y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(2\omega t)$

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Slika 83: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(5\omega t), y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(2\omega t)$

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Slika 103: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(6\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(2\omega t)$

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Slika 111: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(6\omega t), y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(6\omega t)$

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Slika 113: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(6\omega t), y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(7\omega t)$

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Slika 117: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(6\omega t), y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(9\omega t)$

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Slika 120: $x = -4 \operatorname{div} \cos(6\omega t), y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(10\omega t)$

Slika 121: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(7\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(\omega t)$

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Slika 123: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(7\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(2\omega t)$

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Slika 125: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(7\omega t), y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(3\omega t)$

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Slika 129: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(7\omega t), y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(5\omega t)$

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Slika 131: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(7\omega t), y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(6\omega t)$

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Slika 133: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(7\omega t), y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(7\omega t)$

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Slika 137: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(7\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(9\omega t)$

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Slika 139: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(7\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(10\omega t)$

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Slika 141: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(8\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(\omega t)$

Slika 142: $x = -4 \operatorname{div} \cos(8\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(\omega t)$

Slika 143: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(8\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(2\omega t)$

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